

MANAGING GLOBAL GOVERNANCE ACADEMY 2023

CHANGE MAKER PROJECT:

UPSCALING THE MACROECONOMIC MODELING FOR CLIMATE ADAPTATION

PROJECT REPORT

UPSCALING THE MACROECONOMIC MODELING FOR CLIMATE
ADAPTATION

CRED - Climate Resilient Economic Development

German Institute
of Development
and Sustainability

Deutsche Gesellschaft
für Internationale
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OBJECTIVE

This Project Report aims to consolidate the team's work during the Change Maker Project of the Managing Global Governance Academy 2023 that led to its main findings and conclusions presented to the challenge givers - the Climate Resilient Economic Development (CRED)'s team from the GIZ - during the Sounding Board Session on November 23rd 2023.

By consolidating the team's work in a readable format (Word .doc and .PDF files), it becomes easier for the GIZ's CRED team to better explore the team's findings and going further through possible alternative strategies and pathways to upscale the Climate Resilient Economic Development (CRED) Project.

It conveys to highlight that this Report does not replace the prototype delivered on the sounding board session - the Miro board [GIZ Climate CRED, Visual Workspace for Innovation \(miro.com\)](#) -, but rather complement it.

INTRODUCTION

The Change Maker project is part of the Managing Global Governance Academy. The main idea is to make the Academy's participants apply the acquired knowledge and learnings in design-thinking methodology to develop an innovative solution for a real-world challenge that is given to the team by an external actor.

The challenge accepted by the team was proposed by Sebastian Homm and Naima Abdulle, from the GIZ project Climate Resilient Economic Development (CRED) - [Policy Advice for Climate Resilient Economic Development | Internationale Klimaschutzinitiative \(IKI\) \(international-climate-initiative.com\)](#) -, and it was:

“How can we as a GIZ project upscale our approach on climate sensitive macroeconomic modeling and enable emerging and developing countries to expand their own competencies required for comprehensive and transformative adaptation action?”

The team has applied the design-thinking methodology, specifically the two-diamonds scheme (see the image 1 below). During the first phase, the Problem Space, the team's main target was to discover the challenge more accurately, by understanding it and empathizing with the challenge givers and some of their stakeholders, and trying to define and frame possible strategies to solve the problem.

It is important to note that in this situation the “problem” is already given: the difficulty in upscaling the project to other developing countries. Despite not denying that this is a problem, part of the understanding/empathizing stage comprises to verify to what extent the challenge posed is the actual problem regarding the purposes desired by the challenge given.

Acknowledging doesn't know neither the CRED project, its methodology nor the alleged difficulty in connecting with possible new stakeholders in other developing countries, the Challenge Maker's team assumed a beginners' mindset. Therefore, the team sought to know better the CRED project by exploring the vast content/materials on both the GIZ's webpage ([Adapting economic development to climate change - giz.de](https://www.giz.de)) and the CRED's own webpage on International Climate Initiative (IKI) [Policy Advice for Climate Resilient Economic Development | Internationale Klimaschutzinitiative \(IKI\) \(international-climate-initiative.com\)](https://www.international-climate-initiative.com).

Furthermore, the team conducted several interviews, which were quite valuable to help with clustering some of the so-called hindrances to upscale the project and finding the common ground among the team regarding best strategies to present pathways to solve the conundrum. Some premises guided the initial working phase:

- Leaving out any presumptions and escaping from the ladder of inference.
- Being free to question everything;
- Being curious;
- Listening and observing;
- Exploring all themes related and trying to find out possible connections with the challenge given that may lead to a pathway;

In the Problem Space stage, one of the team's main findings was that the problem was not necessarily related to the implementation of the project in the countries where it has been already running (Georgia, Kazakhstan, and Vietnam). Rather, it was related to the negotiating phase. The team used the interviews to check some hypotheses that came out.

These hypotheses and ideas were mainly related to storytelling, the need for a more country-oriented approach strategy; increasing and exploring the network within the

BMZ and GIZ structures, either in German or in its field offices, and connecting to the proper decision-makers who hold the reins to establish the cooperation project within potential target countries.

After reframing the problem, the work phased into the Solution Space. The group followed some suggestions discussed during the ChangeMaker module and benefited from some exercises practiced during that phase. It is worth mentioning the Personas approach and the Solution Tree to support the “ideation”/conception of the prototype.

Considering the entangled net of stakeholders and possible means to address the problem, the team decided to use a flowchart to better present the solution proposed. Thus, the prototype consisted in a flowchart in Miroboard, an app that facilitates the creation, collaboration and design of collaborative projects. In addition, some suggestions encompassed mapping stakeholders and possible projects with whom CRED could share efforts to adapt its narrative and to connect with better stakeholders.

Considering this brief description, the following sections present the team’s work and its main findings. The sections are divided in Problem Space (Discovering/Understanding/Empathizing) and Solution Space (Ideation and Prototype).

PROBLEM SPACE

As no one of the group had previously heard about the Climate Resilient Economic Development project before, it was mandatory knowing the project, its history, some main initiatives, and relevant actions that had already been undertaken under its purview.

In this sense, the team explored the vast content/materials on both the GIZ's webpage ([Adapting economic development to climate change - giz.de](https://www.giz.de/en/press-releases/2024/04/2024-04-23-adapting-economic-development-to-climate-change)) and CRED's own webpage on International Climate Initiative (IKI) [Policy Advice for Climate Resilient Economic Development | Internationale Klimaschutzinitiative \(IKI\) \(international-climate-initiative.com\)](https://www.international-climate-initiative.com/en/policy-advice-for-climate-resilient-economic-development).

It conveys to highlight that the project has astonishing numerous contents, from factsheets and policy briefs to videos, that conspicuously show and explain all relevant information about it. Among others, It is worth mentioning:

- [CRED Publications Overview \(giz.de\)](https://www.giz.de/en/press-releases/2024/04/2024-04-23-adapting-economic-development-to-climate-change)
- [CRED Factsheet: Methods for Assessing and Planning Climate-Resilient Economic Development \(2024\) | Internationale Klimaschutzinitiative \(IKI\) \(international-climate-initiative.com\) - giz2024-en-CRED-factsheet.pdf](https://www.international-climate-initiative.com/en/policy-advice-for-climate-resilient-economic-development)
- [Managing Climate Risks and Adaptation with Macroeconomic Models \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...)
- [Voices from partners on managing climate risks with macroeconomic models \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...)

DISCOVERING the CRED Project

“Climate adaptation can no longer be confined to single sectors (like agriculture) but needs to be mainstreamed into economic decision making. Only such a whole-economy approach to climate adaptation will allow countries to adequately understand and react to the increasing risks which climate change poses for their future national development and social welfare.”

Partner countries:	Georgia, Kazakhstan, Viet Nam (until 03/2023)
Funder:	Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV)
Duration:	01.2019 – 06.2025
Budget:	6,000,000 EUR
Result:	Methods for assessing and planning climate-resilient economic development are available and are being applied for implementing NAPs and the adaptation components of NDCs.

To enable climate-resilient economic development, it is essential that countries strengthen their ability to understand, plan for and continuously manage climate risk for their key economic processes. Macroeconomic modeling can make a major contribution to actionable, evidence-based policy-making for enhancing economic resilience.

However, in many countries, capacities for the assessment of country-specific climate change impacts on economic development via quantitative modeling are insufficient. Policy-makers need reliable economic model for anticipated climate impacts and adaptation

The project consists in assessing the economic impact of climate risks and developing potential adaptation scenarios. CRED project has developed national macroeconomic models that calculate the country-specific impacts of climate change and appropriate adaptation measures on gross domestic product and employment.

By providing evidence-based scenarios regarding adaptation measures undertaken for tackling climate change, it aims to support the decision-making process within the countries in terms of allocating public money, cost-efficiency of public spending, and estimating the impact of their actions on gross domestic product, employment, and the environment.

By that, CRED programme combines capacity building in macroeconomic modeling with advisory services in the use of these modeling results for evidence-based climate-resilient economic policies and strategies. Thus, the implementation of CRED within the countries consisted of:

- 1 - Capacity building: model building training
- 2 - Policy Advice Support
- 3 - Dissemination: international exchange on approach, results and lessons learnt;

UNDERSTANDING the challenging;

“How can we as a GIZ project upscale our approach on climate sensitive macroeconomic modeling and enable emerging and developing countries to expand their own competencies required for comprehensive and transformative adaptation action?”

Although the project is well-structured, based on consistent methodology, and is successfully running in three countries, the challenge givers report difficulties in upscaling the project. Initially, it had a runlife until 31.12.2022, which has been postponed to 2025. It was and still has been crucial finding new partners in order to assure the resources provided by the BMUV and the continuity of the project, thus.

In this sense, there was no doubt about the problem to be solved: try to find some reasons why they have been facing difficulties in expanding the project and to suggest possible pathways to and reach out to new possible-interested stakeholders and circumvent it.

The team conducted interviews with some stakeholders to better understand what would be the hindrances preventing the project from gaining new partners. The interviews were:

- 1st interview: September 2023: The team of Climate Resilient Economic Development (CRED): Mr Sebastian Homm (sebastian.homm@giz.de), the CRED's project coordinator; and Naime Abdulle (naima.abdulle@giz.de), Policy Advice;
- 2nd interview: November 7, 2023, with the GWS - Institute for Economic Structures Research, based in Osnabruck, Germany. Partner institution who developed the E3 economic model used by CRED.
- 3rd interview: November 8, 2023, with the GIZ's ERA project (Thailand and Egypt)
- 4th interview: November 9, 2023, with Dana Yermolyonok, from Kazakhstan, CRED project's focal point in the country.

Interview with CRED team:

- Empathizing with the challenge givers by listening to their opinions and trying to look at the problem through their lens.
- Engaging on the problem posited by contrasting their views with the team's first perceptions.
- Identifying other possible agents that could provide the team with different views and perspectives about the difficulty in upscaling the CRED project.

Some findings from the interview with the CRED team:

- The limitations pointed out by the CRED team were more related to the implementation phase than to the negotiating one. Some of the difficulties

highlighted by the CRED team were tied to the lack of expertise within the countries that weakened the capacity building efforts.

- Also, difficulties in connecting stakeholders from ministries of Planning or Economics, or other that theoretically centralizes the decision-making process or has the political clout to take the decision of establishing the cooperation project;
- Regarding that, the team realizes a sort of misunderstanding about political structure and relation between national institutions in developing countries - which, actually is not much different from developed ones, such as Germany, since the GIZ also has difficulties in sharing information and efforts.
- Hardly has the information been shared smoothly in developing countries in a way that demands from some ministries are naturally taken into account in the budget planning, nor the Ministry of Economy or Planning always take rational decisions allocating the budget according to ministries' needs. In fact, it is also hand-in-hand with networking and storytelling. Therefore, mapping stakeholders to try to establish successful connections is as important as adapting its narrative to the agent approached, since many of those who can take the decisions are not so familiar with economic concepts or are committed to good reasons.
- Unfortunately, it is common that many policy makers have a hidden agenda, not to mention the rising denialism regarding climate change that followed the footsteps of Populism in many countries.
- The team also noticed that the CRED project seemingly applied some of the South-South Cooperation (SSC) principles, such as no conditionings or country-oriented approach respecting demand-driven needs.
- The team realized that the CRED project does not take much advantage from the GIZ network, especially in trying to connect with some GIZ field officers. As some members of the group pointed out, some GIZ field officers, such as the Brazilian, are very important and have already established long standing, sustainable relations with likely right policy-makers within the countries. Thus,

had the CRED team tried to use the GIZ network and connect with local GIZ projects, there would have been more chances of successfully approaching the right decision makers.

- Likewise, the CRED project has little contact with third parties or possible new partners, such as the UN system or Banks of Development, which already have deep-rooted ties within developing countries. In addition, many of them seek funding trilateral cooperation initiatives that could provide exactly what the CRED project offers, such as capacity building.
- In a nutshell,
 - The Change Makers' team extracted some impressions that the CRED team were more concerned about difficulties that came out while the project was already running, relating this to the barriers in replicating the project in other countries.
 - The CRED team has been trying to create its own bridges with national institutions instead of trying to take benefits from the existent network established by both German institutions, especially the GIZ, or international ones, such as from the UN system.
 - The narrative used seemingly is not adapted according to the national stakeholder with whom the CRED talks, either in terms of literacy, the political clout of the stakeholder in influencing the adoption of the international project or the importance given by the stakeholder to climate change and economic modeling in planning.

Very important limitation: the team was not able to interview any stakeholder from countries in which attempts to establish the project failed. Therefore, many of the interviewers' claims about the possible reasons for the failed attempts had no chance of being checked. For instance, what other countries or stakeholders that the CRED team tried to approach and failed?

The Change Makers' team recognizes that the small number of interviewers, all connected to the CRED project, and the absence of interviewers from failed attempted countries weaken some conclusions. Nevertheless, the team believes that

this does not compromise the entire work, for some strategies suggested are still valid hypotheses to upscale the project.

Taking all this into account, at least three things are worth noticing in the problem space phase.

- a) Firstly, a sample of a standard approach-narrative comprised in the CRED publications, which underscores the validity of the arguments used, but it could contemplate a more country-oriented, adapted approach
- b) The main questions made during the interviews and the methodology applied, as well as the way the group extracted and clustered the main observations;
- c) Lastly, some notes and findings from the interview with the GWZ, who built and developed the E3 macroeconomic model used by the CRED. This interview is important for two reasons.
 - i) The simple one, is because the GWZ was not tied to GIZ, but merely a partner, being the only interview with no-GIZ people.
 - ii) Secondly and more importantly, the group was quite aware that neither of us had enough economic knowledge to contest the macroeconomic model or to raise doubts about its accuracy and functioning. After all, the model has been running for years, being used by Germany for decades, and the project was validated and is successfully running in three countries. Therefore, the team assumed that there were no problems or misbeliefs regarding the model functioning. However, some aspects regarding the economic model might have something to do with the challenge posed, such as the understanding about or the belief on its functioning, or the accuracy of the response provided to the country's decision-makers.

A. Example of CRED's narrative:

Macroeconomic assessments of climate change enable governments to take systematic climate action and navigate economic development towards resilience.

- *In many countries, there is a lack of expertise in the model-based assessment of country-specific climate change impacts on economic development. The quantification of the economic effects can support knowledge-based policy decisions, which are necessary for climate-resilient economic policies, investments in future-proof sectors, and effective adaptation planning.*
- *Therefore, the project works with local stakeholders to implement methods and instruments for the calculation of the economic impacts of climate change impacts and their benefits for policy-making. Then, the project makes piloted methods and instruments available to governments and development organizations.*
- *The project promotes international exchange by networking with thematic platforms, providing studies, and making available the lessons learned during the project in a structured form to encourage the replication of the project activities.*
- *The CRED project has developed national macroeconomic models that calculate the country-specific impacts of climate change and appropriate adaptation measures on gross domestic product and employment. Thus, the models show that investments in adaptation measures are effective and profitable.*

B. The questions and the methodology: adapting the 5W2H to frame possible solutions to the problem given;

Taking into account the challenge given, every interview aimed at comprehensively understanding the CRED not only on its conception, methodology or day-to-day running, but also on practical aspects related to the phase before its actual implementation: the negotiation to establish the CRED in other developing countries. Thus, the team's questions and discussions revolved around the following topics:

WHAT...

- What is/are the alleged problem(s) in upscaling the project?
- What are rules that potential-benefited developing countries should respect?
- What is expected from benefited countries to have?

- What are the main resistances from local stakeholders/recipients countries, in your opinion, after you have explained the model?
- What are the main hurdles you face when you try to “sell” the project for new possible countries/stakeholders?
- In what countries do you think that the CRED could be easily implemented? Or in what countries do you like to implement it next?
- What sectors would you choose to map?
- What are the benefits for the German government with this project?
- What do you want to achieve with this whole process?
- What do you expect from us?
- To what extent should we map possible partners?

WHY...

- Why the initial three countries?
- Why is it important for benefitted countries?
- Why is it a problem not upscaling the project?
- Why do you think that other GIZ projects likely-benefited from the CRED’s model do not use it abroad?
- Why do you think that mapping stakeholders could be difficult or a problem?

WHEN...

- When you believe you have to cope with more difficulties by running the project;

WHERE...

- Where does/did the negotiation process take place?
- Where does the training program occur?

WHO...

- Who are both the national stakeholders encompassed on the project in the countries in which it has already been running
- Who and also who are the stakeholders that were approached in the failed attempts

C. 2^o interview 07/11/2023. GWS - Institute for Economic Structures Research, based in Osnabruck, Germany. The E3 model's creator.

The institute develops macroeconomic models to support evidence-based policy making. It has private and public customers at national (Germany) and international level. The GIZ is their client. The macroeconomic model used by the CRED project was developed by the GWS. Some notes below.

- The macroeconomic model used by the CRED belongs to the E3 models developed by the GWS.
- According to the GWS team, the E3 models became increasingly important to evaluate climate change policies.
- The E3 models combined with scenario analysis are suitable tools for quantifying the macroeconomic impact of climate change and the adaptation measures required to cope with it.
- Since the E3 models are embedded in the CRED approach, the Challenge Makers Team seeked know more about the model, especially how it works and what are its limitations and advantages in the view of its own creators.

Main findings and takeaways from this interview:

- The macroeconomic model combines data with energy and emissions data (“E3 modeling”).
- It is based on country-specific data and comprises mid to long-term perspective (until 2050)
- Suitable for scenario analysis (“What if”).
- The model's results show the direct, indirect, and induced economic impacts.
- It is an Excel-base model: easier to structure the model's framework and use it, for it is a well-known interface diminishing the asymmetry of knowledge. Also, equations are programmed in basic visuals for applications.

- It is a tailor-made model, using countries’ specific national data. It is possible to adapt it to local realities.
- Therefore, every model is different.
- Results show a business-as-usual (BAU) projection for all E3 model variables. The BAU is not to be interpreted as a projection in terms of the most realistic development. It serves as a benchmark to compare multiple alternative scenarios.
- Therefore, analyzing the results reliability depends on implementing actual climate change policies.
- Climate hazards affect countries’ sectors differently.
- Input-output model describes the economic structure of the national economy;
- Input-output model describes the relation between producers and consumers, which allows to identify direct, indirect, and income-induced effects.
- The E3 model covers the linkages between the E3’s and enables policy-makers to grasp synergies and trade-offs in adopting certain measures.
- **The model provides data, but the solution belongs to decision-makers.**

“The model doesn’t tell you what to do, but it shows the possible scenarios if some measures had been undertaken. (...)It will not indicate how many jobs have to be cutted in order to achieve certain results”.

Advantages	Alleged main challenges:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cheap: improves cost-benefit of public expenditure. ○ User-friendly: well-know interface ○ No step learning curve; ○ Easy distribution; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The quality of national data; ○ Some countries underestimate the potential results of the model;

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Not a black-box: everyone can have full access to data and the resulting possible scenarios. ○ No previous knowledge in programming is needed for making scenarios analysis. ○ Ensures sustainable capacity-building. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The project requires some expertise, people who are familiar with some topics, especially Economics;
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Diagnosis at the end of the Problem Space:

DIAGNOSIS: Difficulty in attracting and engaging new countries / stakeholders. The challenge revolves around more on the phase of contacting and adopting the project than on its implementation. This difficulty might be due to:

a) Networking and national contacts: attempts of contact concentrates exclusively on the Environmental Ministry, which usually does not exclusively have the political clout to decide about the adoption of an international cooperation project. Many climate change adaptation projects and policies running in developing countries have not been undertaken exclusively by the Ministry of Environment, but by other Ministries.

Hypothesis: Finding more potential stakeholders in other areas/fields/ministries and connecting directly to decision-makers that have the influence to adopt the project will contribute to up-scaling the model. Using the structure of GIZ national officers and/or the BMZ desk officers from countries would help to make the bridge with potential decision-makers. Contacting UN agencies (such as UNDP, ILO, FAO, UNICEF, UNDRR, etc) offices in the countries that are running trilateral international cooperation projects that can benefit from the model and/or can connect them with local stakeholders.

b) Storytelling/ Narrative approach: The current approach focuses primarily on end-users (countries' experts that work in the environmental field and that have economic modeling knowledge). The approach seems to focus more on technical aspects of the model and data requirement (how it works), rather than on what the model can provide (i.e improvement of cost-efficiency of public spending by anti).

Those who have the power to take the decision of adopting the model do not usually have economic, technical knowledge.

Hypothesis: Developing a country-oriented approach and adapting the narrative will enhance the chances of establishing successful connections. By doing a brief, previous research of the country's reality, providing those decision-makers with some samples of evidence-based scenarios of the country in more specific, sensitive, most-needed areas. Highlighting the economic impact of adaptation measures on GDP and other national data if taken;

c) Limited internal communication at GIZ: Limited communication between GIZ headquarters and country offices constrains the leveraging of established relations, limiting the integration of the CRED model in existing and future projects.

Hypothesis: Improving communication between GIZ headquarters and country offices will unlock the full potential of established relationships, fostering a smoother integration of the CRED model. Saving resources within GIZ by avoiding overlapped efforts: many GIZ projects working on climate change may benefit from the use of the CRED model, as the CRED team can benefit from the network and contacts already established by GIZ field offices instead of trying build new relations or reaching out these contacts by its own.

SOLUTION SPACE

THE PROBLEM REFRAMED:

From “How to upscale macroeconomic modeling for Climate Adaptation?” to: **“How to engage a broader spectrum of sectors in recipient countries beyond environmental ministries?”**

This was followed by some of the findings already mentioned, synthesized on the table below. It is important to note that s

Findings	Limitations (related to the prototype)
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GIZ country offices can help to connect with government institutions and other climate-related GIZ projects. ○ GIZ CRED team doesn't have a strong connection with GIZ country offices ○ There is still a gap in ensuring people understanding the relationship of Climate Change and Economy (e.g loss of GDP, employment, etc) ○ Communication about the model's limitations and need for resources (people, budget, time) must be clear from the beginning; ○ Need of approaching the "right" stakeholder/ ministry/institution within targeted countries; ○ The model is complex and need data which is usually difficult to obtain in some countries; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The absence of interviews with GIZ field offices and with stakeholders from the countries whose connection attempts failed. ○ Interviews mainly with GIZ Cred project people, either in Germany or in the countries; ○ Time constraint; ○ Entangled net of relations and possible causes and solutions demanded an attempt of detailed mapping of the whole process; ○ The prototype does not discuss the model or its implementation. Rather, it revolves around more on the strategy to contact stakeholders and establishing the project in new countries;
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The reframed problem lead the team to formulate three central hypotheses to solve the problem:

Hypothesis 1 Limited internal communication at GIZ	Hypothesis 2 Storytelling/ Narrative approach	Hypothesis 3 Networking and national contacts
<p>Enhancing communication between GIZ headquarters and GIZ field offices will capitalize on established relationships, facilitating the integration of the CRED model by other GIZ projects</p> <p>Win-win strategy: some GIZ projects on climate change may benefit from the CRED</p>	<p>Adapting CRED storytelling to a country-specific narrative will boost interest and participation across diverse sectors;</p> <p>Focusing not only on climate change but also on connecting climate change impact to broader aspects: helping possible stakeholders</p>	<p>Attempts of contact concentrate excessively on the Environmental Ministry, which usually does not exclusively have the political clout to decide about the adoption of an international cooperation project, not to mention about allocating a public budget.</p> <p>Finding more potential stakeholders in other areas/fields/ministries and</p>

<p>model. Likewise, the CRED team can benefit from GIZ field offices' network.</p>	<p>to make the bridge between not-seemingly related topics.</p>	<p>connecting directly to decision-makers that have the influence to adopt the project will contribute to upscaling the model.</p>
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IDEATION

The Change Makers team used some tools demonstrated during the CMP module, especially:

- The word cloud: to highlight the frequency of mentions of some words or topics contribute to identifying and detaching the most important from discourses/speeches/interviews;
- Personas and mapping stakeholders:
- Solution Tree: Disentangling the net and connecting the dots.

Word Cloud: clustering words and topics mentioned during the interviews or possibly connected to solutions

Mapping Stakeholders

Why mapping stakeholders can contribute to upscaling the CRED's model:

Stakeholder mapping is a foundational element in project management that significantly contributes to the project's overall success. It facilitates better planning, communication, risk management, and resource utilization, while also ensuring that the project is aligned with the interests and needs of those it impacts or those who can impact it. Furthermore, it helps to visually a user and their world while showing connections within a context, such as an organization and other stakeholders, that might have interest in also embracing the project. Thus, it is a useful tool for finding potential new clients/recipient countries and, thus, upscale the CRED project. Stakeholder maps are a tried-and-true method for driving out project specifics:

1. **Identifying Interests and Influences:** Stakeholder mapping helps in identifying who the stakeholders are and understanding their interests, influence, and potential impact on the project. This understanding is crucial for ensuring that the project aligns with the needs and expectations of the most influential stakeholders. Last but not least, it helps to connect with new potential users and, eventually, upscale the project.
2. **Tailoring Communication Strategies:** Different stakeholders have different needs and preferences for communication. By mapping stakeholders, a project team can develop tailored communication strategies that effectively engage each stakeholder group, ensuring that they are informed and involved appropriately. This is crucial in the proposed country-oriented approach. Showing why it is useful and how it can benefit the countries rather than explain how the model works.
3. **Risk Management:** Understanding stakeholders allows for better anticipation and management of risks. Some stakeholders may oppose or challenge the project, and identifying them early helps in developing strategies to address their concerns and mitigate potential conflicts.
4. **Building Support and Buy-In:** Gaining the support of key stakeholders can be crucial for a project's success. Stakeholder mapping helps identify those whose buy-in is essential and allows the team to focus efforts on building and maintaining these critical relationships. It will contribute for finding new stakeholders.
5. **Resource and Expertise Utilization:** Stakeholders often bring valuable resources and expertise to a project. Identifying and engaging the right stakeholders can provide access to these resources, which can be vital for the success of the project.
6. **Ensuring Sustainability and Long-Term Success:** For projects that aim for sustainability and long-term impact, understanding the stakeholder landscape is crucial. It ensures that the project's outcomes are in line with the long-term goals of key stakeholders, thus enhancing the project's longevity and success.
7. **Legal and Regulatory Compliance:** Some stakeholders, such as government bodies, have regulatory authority over the project. Identifying and engaging with these stakeholders is crucial to ensure that the project complies with all legal and regulatory requirements.

Enhancing Public Relations and Reputation: Engaging with stakeholders effectively can improve the public image and reputation of both the project and the organization behind it. This is especially important in projects that are highly visible or have a significant social impact. This backs the project's reputation and attract attention of other possible user.

Objective: Making better use of the network already established by GIZ field officers will avoid unnecessary efforts and save resources. The CRED project can benefit both from the local contacts provided by the GIZ field officer or the GIZ itself when suggesting some other projects, thus adopting the CRED's economic model to avoid possible overlapping efforts.

As an example, the Change Makers' team used the GIZ's field office in Brazil. Yet the GIZ field office in Brazil is unusually big - as an example, it has more than 3x the number of employees of the German Embassy in Brazil - it has several projects running

at the moment that might benefit from the use of the CRED's economic model (web links below):

Brazil

GIZ local staff

National employees: 248

International employees: 47

Integrated experts: 2

(as at: 31.12.2022)

Brazil and Germany have been pursuing joint projects in the area of sustainable development since 1962. The Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH has been working in Brazil since 1993 and maintains a country office in the capital, Brasília.

Brazil has a crucial role to play in global climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation. The country is home to around 20 per cent of the planet's animal and plant species and its tropical rainforests store huge amounts of greenhouse gases. However, the Amazon, Cerrado savannah and Atlantic Forest areas are under pressure. Illegal mining, livestock farming and large-scale monocultures are destroying extensive forest areas.

Brazil gets much of its energy from hydropower plants. The country has also significantly expanded its wind and solar power capacity over the past 10 years and wants to exploit the considerable potential of these

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- [Supporting Brazil's adaptation to climate change - giz.de](#)
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PROTOTYPE:

[GIZ Climate CRED, Visual Workspace for Innovation \(miro.com\)](#)

The team's prototype aimed to provide a country-oriented approach strategy. As a prototype not aimed at being tested, the team considered a "model 1.0", the first step to explore some of the alternative strategies and pathways indicated. Below one can see what it IS and IS NOT; what it DOES and DOES NOT:

PROTOTYPE: A country-oriented approach strategy. An alternative pathway, a shortcut through already existing means (GIZ field officers), to connect to / engage with stakeholders and influential decision-makers from other sectors/fields/ministries that could benefit from the use of the model.

What the prototype IS:

- Practical flowchart, interactive guideline to provide a tailor-made, customized country-oriented approach to connect with countries' more influential stakeholders;
- In-house solution to enhance country-oriented approach by addressing countries needs;
- Country-oriented approach; connecting directly to national stakeholders not exclusively from Environment Ministries.
- Country-oriented approach focused on what the CRED model is able to do and provide (the economic impact of adaptation measures and how it is useful for improving the cost-efficiency of public spending) rather than highlight how it does what it promises to do.

"When NASA comes to the Parliament asking for a budget, they do not explain how their rockets go to outer space, they just say they want to reach the Moon or Mars".

What the prototype DOES:

- Helps to reflect on internal communication, identifying itself within the structure in which it is a part (GIZ), and how to use better the capacity and capabilities created by its own institution;
- Highlighting that increasing the interaction between the CRED project and GIZ other department and national offices is a win-win game: on the one hand, the CRED team benefits from the network, contacts, and political influence already established by GIZ locally; on the other hand, GIZ can spread CRED economic model to other climate change-related projects avoiding overlapped efforts and, thus, saving resources.

- Indicates how to use better the network already established by GIZ;
- Contributes to the awareness that the decision-making process in developing countries is usually complex and sometimes not concentrated in one Ministry, and if it is, hardly will it be the Ministry of Environment.
- Facilitates the internal process;
- Builds on existing common materials and try to provide the best cost-efficient solution by using the materials (videos, papers, fact sheets) already developed by the CRED project;
- Put all sectors on the same page;

What the prototype IS NOT:

- Just a communication piece or solution;
- A solution in itself;
- Just a text presentation;

What the prototype DOES NOT:

- Focus only on the model nor raise questions about the model;
- Provides inputs to the model, but to the strategy of connecting to new countries/stakeholders in order to increasing the use/adoption of the model
- Restrains the process flow or limited new ideas/solutions realized during its using;

Miro board prototype: the flowchart applying the solution tree

Justifying the Miro Board ([GIZ Climate CRED, Visual Workspace for Innovation \(miro.com\)](https://www.miro.com))

- The mirror board produces a more linear, coherent vision out of messy problems, its possible causes and solutions.

- During the stage of framing the problem, the team realized that it was a complex problem, with many possible actors engaged either in the causes or in the possible solutions, as well as possibly related to a myriad of varieties not necessarily interconnected. Presenting it visually, in a mirror skeleton connecting the bones, would be easier to not only realize what the team grasped, but also to go further in developing new pathways.
- Attempt to communicate our assessment in a more conspicuous, impactful and meaningful way by using illustrative visuals to reinforce one of our main findings: the narrative and the need for new, adapted/adjusted storytelling according to the stakeholders approached.
- The visual image of the problem, its connections and possible solutions help to create bias toward action over freezing by rethinking how to move out.

CONCLUSION

The Change Makers' team is very proud of the chance to address the challenge "Upscaling Macroeconomic Model for Climate Adaptation", posited by the Climate Resilient Economic Development team of the GIZ, as part of the Change Maker Project at the Managing Global Governance Academy 2023.

The challenge provided the team with not only the chance of applying design-thinking methodology and new concepts learnt during the Academy, but also getting familiar with this remarkable project. The CRED economic model signifies a pivotal step towards integrating climate resilience into macroeconomic planning and development strategies. Undoubtedly, every Change Maker involved in this challenge will benefit from this opportunity.

We extend our deepest gratitude to IDOS for their visionary leadership and unwavering support throughout this project. Special thanks are due to the coordinator of the MGG Academy, and lucky for us also our coach, Tatjana Reiber, whose guidance has been instrumental in steering the 2023 MGG Academy towards its successful completion. As our coach, she deserves special mention for her dedication, expertise, and insights, which have been invaluable in navigating the complexities of this endeavor. Additionally, we acknowledge the significant contributions of the challenge givers from the Climate Resilient Economic Development project of the GIZ, whose expertise and challenges have enriched our project, making it not only a learning experience but also a practical tool for fostering sustainable economic development in the face of climate change in our own realities.

This project underscores the critical importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, innovative thinking, and global governance in crafting solutions that are not only sustainable but also inclusive and adaptable to the multifaceted impacts of climate change. It is a testament to what can be achieved when diverse groups come together with a common purpose and a shared commitment to making a difference in the world. We look forward to the continued impact of this project and the further advancements it will inspire in the field of climate-adaptive economic modeling.